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THE METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR ASSESSING THE SUSTAINABILITY OF REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Abstract. The article suggests the methodological framework for assessing the sustainability of regional development. The framework provides an integral estimate, which includes regional social, economic and ecological development indices on the proportional basis, and enables the assessment of the territory's development sustainability level. The findings are illustrates for the Bielaviezha Ecological Region (BER).

Keywords: methodological framework; sustainable development; region.

The problem of regional sustainable development appears to be highly relevant for Belarus and other countries. The acknowledgement of the urgency of the transition to “green” economy and addressing complex social, economic and ecological issues for a certain territory encourages research in sustainable development including the approaches to assessing the sustainability of regional development [1, p. 60].

The most reasonable solution for assessing the sustainability of the development of a region or a territory would be an integral estimate, which implies calculating a number of indices.

The sustainability index (the integral index) can be calculated as the geometric mean value, which reflects the proportional balance of partial indicators of regional development:

$$I_s = \sqrt[3]{I_{soc} \cdot I_{econ} \cdot I_{ecol}}$$

where I_s – the sustainability index; I_{soc} – the social development index; I_{econ} – the economic development index; I_{ecol} – the ecological development index.

The partial indices reflect the ratio of the actual development of the region to the target (normative) value of the indicator for Belarus in accordance with the National Strategy of the Sustainable Social and Economic Development of the Republic

of Belarus until 2020 [2, p. 196–199].

The calculation of the social development index is based on life expectancy, the economic development index is based on labour productivity as value added per person employed, and the ecological development index is based on the environmental performance index that embraces environmental health and ecosystem vitality sub-indices.

The suggested approach was illustrated for the Bielaviezha Ecological Region extending over Kamianets and Pruzhany districts of Brest region and Svislach district of Hrodna region.

The source data for the sustainability assessment of the development of the Bielaviezha Ecological Region are provided in Table 1.

Table 1 – The source data for the sustainability assessment of the BER development

Indicators	Bielaviezha Ecological Region			Belarus (target values for 2020)
	2012	2013	2013/ 2012	
Life expectancy, years	72,4	72,8	1,006	73
Value added per person employed, deflated into 2012 prices, BYR million	85,4	87,7	1,027	163,2
Environmental Performance Index	0,674	0,677	1,004	1,0

Table 2 provides the results of the integral assessment. The growth of the social, economic and ecological development indices for the region as well as the integral index proves the progress in attaining to the target values of sustainability development indicators.

Table 2 – The sustainability assessment of the BER development

Indicators	Bielaviezha Ecological Region		
	2012	2013	2013/ 2012
Social Development Index	0,992	0,997	1,005
Economic Development Index	0,523	0,537	1,027
Ecological Development Index	0,674	0,677	1,004
Sustainable Development Index	0,705	0,713	1,011

The results of the integral assessment of the development sustainability are interpreted according to the presented scale of I_S values (see Table 3).

Table 3 – Sustainability Levels of Regional Development

Sustainability Level	Threshold Values of the Integral Index	Assessment Interpretation
1	$0,8 < I_S \leq 1,0$	High sustainability
2	$0,6 < I_S \leq 0,8$	Sustainable development
3	$0,4 < I_S \leq 0,6$	Insufficient sustainability
4	$0,2 < I_S \leq 0,4$	Unsustainable development
5	$0 < I_S \leq 0,2$	Social and economic crisis

Therefore, the assessment results indicate the sustainable development of the Bielaviezha Ecological Region.

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МЕТОДИКА ОЦЕНКИ УРОВНЯ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ РЕГИОНА

Аннотация. В статье предложена методика оценки уровня устойчивости развития региона, которая позволяет получить интегральную оценку, пропорционально включающую индексы социального, экономического и экологического развития региона, и определить степень устойчивости развития территории. Приведены результаты апробации методики на примере Беловежского экологического региона (БЭР).

Ключевые слова: методика оценки; устойчивое развитие; регион.